

D 6.5. Report on the gEneSys engagement with and impact on the wider energy transition landscape

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Abstract	This report explains how the project engaged with influential change actors, stakeholders, and change recipients in sharing knowledge and building consensus on credible pathways and solutions to energy transition with equitable, fair, and just outcomes, presented from an intersectional and interdisciplinary perspective on gender inequality.

Document history

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1. BACKGROUND

The gEneSys strategy for engagement with the wider energy transition landscape of influential actor and stakeholder organisations focused on the expectations identified in the evaluation report of the gEneSys proposal. The report stressed the importance of the project for:

- Building evidence
- Advancing scholarly understanding
- Identifying powerholders
- Facilitating international cooperation between Africa and Europe
- Connecting gender perspectives and energy
- Demonstrating that policy is under-researched
- Demonstrating the urgency of including gender perspectives in advancing low energy systems
- Demonstrating intersectional and inclusive analytical approach with impact on policy design

Listed below are explanations on how gEneSys used engagement of target actor and stakeholder communities in advancing equitable, just, and sustainable energy transition outcomes.

2. ENGAGEMENT TO COLLECT AND PROMOTE EVIDENCE AND ADVANCE SCHOLARLY UNDERSTANDING OF GENDER ISSUES IN ENERGY TRANSITION

gEneSys produced novel survey results on working conditions and career perceptions in the energy transition ecosystem. Invitations to support dissemination of these surveys to potential recipients included links to the project's website and the results reported in the Zenodo platform. Communications were sent individually to approximately 150 contact persons/offices listed on the: [NCPs Horizon Europe portal](#); national members of the [European Students Union](#); the [IGNITE Network+](#), and participants in the workshop on [Gender Balance in Energy Transition R&I](#) (funded by DG CINEA).

The same information with links to the gEneSys website were sent as individual emails to around 200 **academic researchers** located in EU universities and beyond, working in areas directly relevant to the mission of the gEneSys project to promote gender perspective on power relations in energy transition, who published research findings during the period 2023-2025.

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The aim of this approach was to mobilise interest and response to the research evidence gEneSys was producing and to introduce researchers working in the energy transition sphere who were apparently not familiar with gender analysis methods to the benefits of applying the gender analytical approaches gEneSys has advanced in their own work.

Another **community of scholars** that gEneSys has engaged with included experts on developing indicators to measure impact of advances in science and innovation, which were discussed at the **STI conference in Leiden**, where gEneSys organised a special session on gendered indicators for energy transition.

In addition, information about gEneSys research was communicated to the **Association of European Renewable Energy Research Centres (EUREC)**, and the **European Energy Research Alliance (EERA)**. Representatives of both organisations were regularly invited to participate in the open events organised by gEneSys. These included webinar on *Gender Balance and Gendered Power Relations in Energy Transition. Stakeholder consultation on new research findings and recommendations (December 2023)*; on-line round-table on *Gender-Energy nexus In the African / European energy transition efforts (June 2024)*; *Integrating Gender Dimension and Equality Objectives into Energy and Deep Tech Fields for Inclusive and Sustainable Future (October 2024)*; *proposal for a policy session at EUSEW 2025*; *gEneSys Autumn School (October 2025)*; *gEneSys final conference*.

The gEneSys **Autumn School in October 2025** attracted high demand for attendance among your researchers from around the world (North and South America, Africa, Asia, Australia). In total 162 applications were received but only 21 places were available. 44% of the applicants were from non-EU countries. The course provided fellows from various disciplines - scientists, engineers, economists, sociologists, anthropologist, political scientists, journalists and communicators - with a training opportunity which merged science with society and delivered an overview on the future of energy. The school explored the deep interconnections between the need to change the way energy is produced and consumed, and the social dynamics inherent in this process. Post event survey of participants' views highlighted the importance of interdisciplinary research approaches but also the presence of barriers to participation such as complex visa procedures and lack of grants for training.

Lastly, working with the **University of Trento**, gEneSys team introduced to **Energy and Society Network** as the co-organising partner, a methodology promoting awareness of gender aspects in energy transition.

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3. ENGAGEMENT TO IDENTIFY AND INTERACT WITH POWERHOLDERS

Information about the project was communicated to the EU Member States **Permanent Representations** in Brussels. Representatives with Energy portfolio received invitations to participate in the project's two joint webinars and help with the dissemination of the surveys.

The **European Sustainable Energy Week (EUSEW)** annual event website was targeted and monitored to identify "powerholders". Wherever the contact information was available using public access, relevant participants were contacted directly with information about the project and offered support on applying gender analysis methods in their domain of work. The websites of **EUREC** and **EERA** were equally monitored to identify which of their members could be considered as powerholders to advance impact of the gEneSys project.

The relevant 'powerholders' were the Project Officers in the relevant **DGs, e.g. CINEA, Energy, RTD, EMPL, and INTPA**, as well as identifiable through publicly available information Policy Advisers in the Commission.

A special stakeholder invited to the gEneSys events was **CENCENELEC**, an association of National Standards Organisations. CENCENELEC was targeted because of its Europe wide reach and in recognition of their efforts to promote **gender responsive standardisation**.

This inclusion was made in recognition that European standards play a crucial role in energy transformation as tools to enhance safety and performance, improve energy efficiency, and protect consumers, workers, and the environment.

International Energy Agency (IEA) was also on the priority 'powerholders' target list for communication and dissemination activities and for invitation to gEneSys events. IEA has been **monitoring gender gap in energy** and publishing these on their website.

4. ENGAGEMENT TO FACILITATE INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION BETWEEN AFRICA AND EUROPE

The aim of the gEneSys' efforts to advance international cooperation on energy transition was to identify opportunities, gaps, and barriers to transform dominant

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power and gender relations by advancing socio-technological research and interventions for development that produce gender equality benefits.

African Conference on Women Engineers and Scientists in 2024, which was co-hosted by the **Rwandan Association of Women in Science and Engineering (RAWISE)**, **Africa Regional Network of INWES and AIMS**, and aligned with their missions to enhance diversity, equity, and inclusion in STEM.

Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI) the **GGGI** states its commitment as “*Rights. Justice. Action. For ALL Women and Girls.*” As climate change disproportionately affects vulnerable populations, GGGI is spearheading gender-transformative solutions across its member countries to ensure that the green transition is both sustainable and inclusive.

Gender Summit 2023 – Africa’s Energy Transition Pathways through the Gender Lens consisted of two days of on-line event and two days of in-person meeting in Accra. It was an opportunity to introduce gEneSys to experts and practitioners advancing energy transition in Africa. The report and recommendations can be found [here](#).

Science Granting Councils Initiative on strengthen the capacities in Sub-Saharan Africa to advance systemic change towards greater gender inclusivity in the science technology and innovation (STI) sector.

World Bank/ESMAP/WEN Africa - Women in Energy Network Africa (WEN-Africa) initiative was created in 2024, with the objective to increase the overall female professional’s participation in the energy sector with special focus on technical and leadership roles in the Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) fields.

CEI-Africa initiative includes a programme dedicated to advancing women’s leadership and participation within the clean energy sector, recognising the vital role women play in driving sustainable change.

Transforming Energy Access Learning Partnerships (TEA-LP) shares gEneSys’ interest in improving Master course curricula, as well as the EUA goals to improve postgraduate training. Although, gEneSys also examined school curricula and found ‘old-fashioned’ narratives that diverged in a significant way from available research.

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5. ENGAGEMENT TO CONNECT GENDER PERSPECTIVES WITH VISIONS OF CREDIBLE ENERGY TRANSITION PATHWAYS

gEneSys promotes the idea that credible and sustainable pathways to equitable, just and inclusive energy transition should be defined through consensus and co-creation processes involving relevant change actors and result in outcomes that are measurable and socially responsible.

International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) sees women as community anchors, household managers, and frontline bearers of energy poverty, who are disproportionately affected by energy access challenges, but remain underrepresented in renewable energy design, deployment, and decision-making.

The Global Women's Network for Energy Transition (GWNET) empowers women in energy through interdisciplinary networking, advocacy, training, and mentoring to promote gender-sensitive action around the energy transition in all parts of the world.

Kelso Institute facilitates sustainable energy transition including consumer co-ownership in renewables. The core questions are about ownership and privatisation, insolvency and restructuring, digitisation and ICT, and financial crises.

Women Engage for a Common Future (WECF) promotes a gender just and healthy planet for all. It is an international network of over 250 women's and civil society organisations in 70 countries who believe that a sustainable future and environment need holistic solutions reflecting the lives of people on the ground.

CEDEFOP fosters gender equality in VET and lifelong learning as essential competencies for ensuring that all individuals can access and benefit from quality education and career opportunities in energy and more widely.

RESCOOP is a European federation of energy communities, a growing network of 2,500 energy communities from across Europe with 2 million citizens active in the energy transition.

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6. ENGAGEMENT TO PROMOTE INTEGRATION OF GENDER EQUALITY MAINSTREAMING INTO ENERGY TRANSITION POLICY

The primary focus in using gEneSys evidence to support gender equality mainstreaming has been to cooperate with **European Energy Research Alliance (EERA)**. Representatives were invited to participate in the open events organised by gEneSys (two on-line events, two conferences and the Autumn School) and were regularly updated on gEneSys outcomes by directed to the project website.

Also invited to gEneSys events were representatives of the **EIT InnoEnergy**, because EIT invests in early-stage companies and advances workforce to drive sustainable economic growth but also has **gender equality policy in place**.

The **European Innovation Council (EIC)** Board has been also a target because of its commitment to advancing gender equality across Europe's innovation ecosystem. EIC champions **Women Leadership Programme and Women TechEU**, and invested €363 million in women-led deep tech companies over four years.

Energy SHIFTS - "Energy Social sciences & Humanities Innovation Forum Targeting the SET-Plan" - contributes knowledge on research to understand societal needs and developing Europe's leadership in using and applying energy-related Social Sciences and Humanities (energy-SSH). gEneSys demonstrated the need to explicitly ask questions about the gender dimension.

7. ENGAGEMENT TO FACILITATE INTERSECTIONAL AND INCLUSIVE ANALYTICAL APPROACH TO CREATING JUST AND EQUITABLE OUTCOMES

gEneSys reached out beyond the traditional audiences of actors and stakeholders in energy transition to involve Deep Tech community through a joint conference between gEneSys and the **NET4Air** Horizon Europe project, whose mission is to advance nanoelectronics-based devices, nanotechnology, and smart systems integration for applications in environmental monitoring, communication, and data processing. The aim was to explore the gender aspects that can be communicated to the projects centred on technology solutions. The highly participatory event improved understanding on how to explain and communicate evidence and knowledge on gender dimension and equality in research fields not (historically)

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familiar with gender issues. Discussions produced policy recommendations captured in a [policy brief](#) available on the Zenodo platform.

The [LEAP-RE](#) programme was one of the core targets for gEneSys because it funded over 30 research and capacity-building projects designed to contribute to the AU–EU Innovation Agenda, the Africa–EU Green Energy Initiative, and the Global Gateway’s sustainable energy pillar. gEneSys explored opportunities for collaboration by joining the LEAP-RE web portal, organising a joint webinar, and inviting LEAP-RE to gEneSys external events.

[European Universities Association](#) (EUA) produced the ‘Roadmap for European Universities in Energy’, building on the SET-Plan Education and Training Roadmap. This involved consultation with more than 300 experts in the field, located in 500 European universities. Their conclusions propose a new approach to Master and Doctoral level training, which is interdisciplinarity and includes social science but does **not** recognise gender and social inequalities.

Dialogue with the [Energy Community](#) Secretariat on sex-disaggregated gender data in energy fields. Where gEneSys could provide information on the attractiveness of the workplace and on gender-aware policies and initiatives.

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